

LINKS AMONG ELECTRONIC WORD OF MOUTH, DESTINATION IMAGE AND INTENTION TO REVISIT: A STUDY IN TRA VINH OF VIETNAM

QUANG LINH HUYNH

Ho Chi Minh City University of Food Industry, Vietnam; Email: linhhq@hufi.edu.vn

Abstract

Visitors' intention to revisit tourism attractions is extremely significant to the local tourism industry. The aim of the current research is to scrutinize the causal relations among electronic word of mouth, destination image and visitors' intention to revisit the tourism attraction where they already visited. The research was undertaken with 500 visitors visiting the Tra Vinh city of Vietnam. The empirical outcomes discover that, electronic word of mouth and destination image can improve visitors' intention to revisit the tourism attraction. Additionally, electronic word of mouth can enhance visitors' perception on destination image. The current research is expected to be helpful to administrators by providing an improved understanding of the casual relation among electronic word of mouth, destination image and visitors' intention to revisit the tourism attraction. Accordingly, they could establish better policies on improving visitors' intention to revisit local tourism attractions.

Keywords: Electronic word of mouth; Destination image; Intention to revisit

INTRODUCTION

According to (Sadeh et al., 2012), tourism has brought numerous benefits to local residents and administrations due to the creation of plentiful jobs, which could increase local residents' income, therefore, improving governmental returns. Several nations regard it as one of the major industries there. In addition, Kanwel et al. (2019) emphasized tourism as an increasingly influential sector all over the world, which extremely affects the economy of a nation; whereas, Ramseook-Munhurrun (2016) highlighted the vital role of tourist destinations for developing local tourism industries, which is an arrangement of both tourism products and services. This arrangement will provide tourists with a special traveling experience. Sadeh et al. (2012) contended that, tourists' revisiting intention to the destination is one of the key elements contributing to the sustainable and successful development in the tourism industry. Furthermore, Huynh (2018) implied that, various countries deem tourists' revisiting intention to the destination as a substantial point for developing the tourism industry. Drawing visitors and maintaining their revisiting intention is one of the main factors leading to thriving tourism development (Mai & Nguyen, 2015).

The revolutions and fluctuations in technology, demographic transitions, as well as economic and social developments are governing factors, which can lead to more involvement in diverse tourism destinations that have been on the increase (Eugenio-Martin et al, 2004). It could not discuss traveling and tourism if it does not take into account the chief part, which makes all the remaining parts fit into this big aenigma called tourists. Given the fact that traveling experiences are obtained at tourism destinations, various academics have defined both tourism

destinations and other indispensable aspects which any destination would take into consideration to struggle with other tourism destinations. For instance, a strong brand of tourism destination can be regarded as one of the most competitive advantages. Because tourism is one of the most energetic industrial sectors, various have analyzed and explained the whole phenomenon, its causes and effects. Nonetheless, tourism research is not about economic indexes, but also about influential indexes which result in these outcomes. Some of them are the reasons and motivations which lead to the traveling of tourists. Consequently, tourism industry has become a sustainable channel for growth that can lead to numerous effects and stimulate developments in other industries (Srivastava & Rai, 2013).

Furthermore, tourism extremely advances local infrastructure. In addition, Jayawardena (2002) designated the tourism future is mostly dependent on national capability by providing extremely able tourism products to please unceasingly changing preferences and expectations as well as the increasing requirements among travelers. Prior studies have been undertaken on potential travelers at home nation. In contradiction of the distinctive approach, it can recommend intention to revisit would be taken at tourism destination with real travelers. Numerous scholars adopt that approach to analyze intention to revisit (Guntoro & Hui, 2013; Marinkovic et al., 2014). Further, Nguyen (2014) asserted that, the province of is a seaside area situated in Vietnam's Mekong Delta, bordering to Ben Tre, Vinh Long and Soc Trang provinces as well as the East Sea with a population of around 1.1 million people and an area of nearly 2300 square kilometers. Moreover, Huynh (2018) claimed Tra Vinh province enjoys a variety of natural and man-made tourism resources as well as various favorable conditions, which are appropriate for developing tourism. Tra Vinh province is one of the most significant tourism destinations of Vietnam due to its strategic location and uniqueness.

Therefore, to help Tra Vinh of Vietnam sustainably develop its tourism destinations, studies on tourists' revisiting intention to the local tourism destinations is imperative to be conducted. To fill this gap, the current project seeks to identify factors that determine visitors' revisiting intention to the Tra Vinh city of Vietnam; then develop a theoretical research model to investigate the impacts of those influences on visitors' intention to revisit the tourism destinations in the Tra Vinh city of Vietnam with the data gathered there. The rest of the current research is arranged as below. In section 2, it summarizes the literature related to tourists' revisiting intention and develops the research hypotheses on the influential factors on visitors' intention to revisit tourism destinations in the Tra Vinh city of Vietnam. Then section 3 presents research methods that are employed for analyses. The research findings are demonstrated in section 4 then some conclusions are given in the final section.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Destination image is a communicating supposed system of thoughts, spirits, conceptions, and purposes to an end point (Rajesh, 2013). In addition, Lopes (2011) referred to destination image as a concept as expressing all impartial knowledge, biases, fancy and emotive thoughts of a person or group about a specific place. Destination image could affect travelers in deciding their tour, behavior at the destination and the enjoyment and recollection of the experience and

picture of the zone provided to travelers feels less vital than the existence of a picture on individual attention (Pantouw & Pangemanan, 2014). Destination image is a vital determinant of the tourism attraction because a sound image of the tourism attraction can bring more travelers to the tourism attraction (Pratminingsih et. al, 2014). Destination image is a thought of a tourist about their trip in the form of information, spirits, and insights into the overall goal, thinking of the experience based on their satisfaction with the tourism attraction where the tourist stayed (Wibowo et al., 2016). Destination image is referred to as a person's overall awareness or the whole set of impressions of a destination (Phelps, 1986). It is deemed as the mental interpretation of an attraction (Alhemoud & Armstrong, 1996).

Electronic word of mouth was mentioned by Umamy et al. (2016) as a word of mouth communication that is the view of numerous people as well as the conversation of thoughts among them. According to Hennig-Thurau et al. (2004), electronic word of mouth is also regarded as a kind of marketing communication that covers declarations of past and future customers on a product or service available to various people online. It is an extremely tool for customers to deliver their feelings and regarded more operative than word of mouth due to the convenience and broader range than old-style word of mouth (Jalilvand & Samiei, 2012; Doosti et al. 2016). Electronic word of mouth is different from traditional one due to the media utilized, the variety of information as well as the range of communication with associated network users (Jeong & Jang, 2011).

Intention to revisit is a driver enabling someone to pay attention to others (Widagdyo, 2017). Furthermore, Jeon (2013) referred to intention to revisit as a vital determinant for ongoing to make organizational profits from a lasting viewpoint. Interest is a determinant of an individual's incentive to do favorite activities which can affect a growing market share. Numerous factors are related to someone's interest that can decide their intention to revisit a destination. Nguyen Viet et al. (2020) defined intention to revisit a tourist attraction as a kind of post-usage behavior; whereas Baker and Crompton (2000) referred it as a tourist repeating an action or revisiting a tourism attraction.

Links among destination image, electronic word of mouth and intention to revisit

Litvin et al. (2008) referred electronic word of mouth as constructive or undesirable statements made by past, current and potential clients about a product/ service that are made available to various people as well as institutions via online. Electronic word of mouth is viewed as a vital information source that affects travelers' traveling intention and their choice of the tourism attraction (Ying & Chung, 2007; Soderlund & Rosengren, 2007; Jalilvand & Samiei, 2012). The recent empirical results demonstrated diverse influences of internet reviews on the product of companies. Such as, several researchers (Chevalier & Mayzlin, 2006; Ye et al., 2011) also showed internet reviews impose an important effect on online purchases. Reviews from customers or tourists in sharing an evaluation attitude could directly influence their intentions to repurchase or revisit (Jalilvand et al., 2013). Based on Abubakar et al. (2017), declarations in electronic word of mouth could influence an individual's faith in intentions to revisit. Faith is the belief which a person likely finds what is wanted in a partner (MS& Rouly, 2020). Faith involves an individual's readiness to act in a convinced way due to the belief which their partner

can deliver what they think. Honesty is an individual's trust which the enterprise agrees in good trust on the quality of products/ services provided to its customers.

Because internet tourist reviews are a vital source of information to both tourists and traveling companies, academics have tried to investigate internet tourist reviews by erudite technologies (Ye et al., 2009). Likewise, Vermeulen and Seegers (2009) indicated internet traveling reviews can affect the decisions of tourists and that positive reviews could enhance the attitudes of tourists towards destinations. In addition, Castaneda et al. (2009) emphasized tourists' attitude toward the network in amplifying customer behavior. Furthermore, Jalilvand and Samiei (2012) revealed electronic word of mouth is an imperative determinant of travelers who meaningfully influence their attitude towards destinations. In addition, Dennis et al. (2009) established a theoretical model to explicate clients' behavior. Clients' intention to rebuy is determined by positive attitudes of clients to services. The importance of information sources were indicated by Hanlan and Kelly (2005) in forming destination image. The outcomes showed that destination image is predominantly created via electronic word of mouth as well as self-governing information sources. Destination image could be established according to the approximation of an area's characteristics. For example, Tasci et al. (2007) asserted the image of an attraction could be affected by advertising information from that attraction.

Additionally, Morgan et al. (2003) declared the negative electronic word of mouth has an overwhelming impact on an attraction image, because dissatisfied tourists feast unbecoming notes in interrelation to their experiences. Correspondingly, empirical research showed electronic word of mouth could influence attraction image (Echtner & Ritchie, 2003; Tasci & Gartner, 2007; Balakrishnan et al., 2011). Further, electronic word of mouth works as a standard for other attractions. Commendations could work as a replacement for faithfulness and could result in destination effectiveness (Reichheld, 2003). For example, Baloglu and McCleary (1999) contended the commendations of a word of mouth from relatives are the most significant information to form tourism images. Likewise, Beerli and Martin (2004) agreed electronic word of mouth should be regarded as the most credible and frank channel of interaction that destination image meaningfully affects. The existing literature of tourism recommends the image of tourism attraction is important not only to travelers' selection of tourism attractions and their subjective perception; but also to the following assessment of the journal as well as to their intentions to revisit (Lin et al., 2007; Hsu et al., 2010; Ryu et al., 2007; Castro et al., 2007).

Additionally, preceding scholars maintained the image of tourism attraction is a significant determinants to explain tourists' intention to revisit the tourism attraction where they already came (Alcaniz et al., 2005; Bigné et al., 2001). Whereas Lin et al. (2007) indicated a preferred image of a tourism attraction strengthens visitors' favorites for the tourism attraction; Ryu et al.'s (2007) emphasized the association between the image of tourism attraction and tourists' behavioral intention to revisit. Furthermore, other researchers showed the image of tourism attraction is the key determinant of tourists' intention to choose the tourism attraction (Phau et al., 2010; Lee, 2009). Overall, it could recommend the hypotheses as below: (1) H1. Electronic

word of mouth can determine Destination image; (2) H2: Destination image can determine Intention to revisit; (3) H3. Electronic word of mouth can determine Intention to revisit.

RESEARCH METHOD

Variables: The three key variables were used for the research model, which are Electronic word of mouth (MEW), Destination image (DEI) and Intention to revisit (TRE). The fourteen items of the three key variables were estimated grounded on a five-point Likert scale from strongly disagrees to very agree. There are six observed dimensions for Electronic word of mouth (MEW), 5 observed dimensions for Destination image (DEI) and three observed dimensions for Intention to revisit (TRE). The variables and their items are adapted and modified from Jalilvand et al. (2012).

Electronic word of mouth (MEW) was measured on six items: (1) MEW1: I regularly read other visitors' online traveling reviews to know which attractions make sound impressions on others; (2) MEW2: To ensure choosing the right attraction (such as the Tra Vinh city of Vietnam), I regularly read other visitors' online traveling reviews; (3) MEW3: I frequently consult other visitors' online traveling reviews to select an attraction; (4) MEW4: I regularly collect information from visitors' online traveling reviews before traveling to a specific attraction; (5) MEW5: If I don't read visitors' online traveling reviews when traveling to an attraction, I am often worried about my choice; (6) MEW6: visitors' online traveling reviews make me more confident in traveling to an attraction (such as the Tra Vinh city of Vietnam).

Destination image (DEI) was calculated on five items: (1) DEI1: the Tra Vinh city of Vietnam is safe and secure; (2) DEI2: The Tra Vinh city of Vietnam provides inspiring and fascinating attractions to visit; (3) DEI3: the Tra Vinh city of Vietnam has attractive landscape as well as natural destinations; (4) DEI4: the Tra Vinh city of Vietnam has a pleasant climate; (5) DEI5: As a tourist attraction, the Tra Vinh city of Vietnam offers good value for money.

Intention to revisit (IRE) was computed 3 items: (1) IRE1: I predict I will visit the Tra Vinh city of Vietnam in the future; (2) IRE2: I would visit the Tra Vinh city of Vietnam rather than any other tourist attraction; (3) IRE3: If everything is as expected, I intend to visit the Tra Vinh city of Vietnam in the coming time.

Sampling: The current work interviewed 500 tourists at 10 chief tourism attractions in the Tra Vinh city of Vietnam. At each of the tourism attractions, 50 tourists were asked for completing the survey forms with the convenience sampling procedure. The ultimate sample encompassed 347 valued answers from informers.

Analyses: Grounded on the aim of research, the quantitative analytic technique was chiefly used for the current research work. The first procedures were reliability analyses for inspecting the properties of variable measurements and items making up the chief variables. The second procedures were exploratory factor analyses. It is a conventional official dimension model which is utilized when both measured and latent variables are supposed to be calculated at the interval level. Subsequently, multiple regression analyses were applied to scrutinize the proposed research hypotheses.

RESULTS

Reliability analyses

The inner reliability of variables was explored by using reliability analyses. Only the variables being made of various items were assessed with reliability analyses. The variables comprising various items are Electronic word of mouth (MEW), Destination image (DEI), and Intention to revisit (IRE). The empirical findings of reliability analyses are revealed in Table 1. According to Murtagh (1990), the lowest apposite threshold of the Cronbach's α s had better be 0.7; whereas the highest Cronbach's α s "if item removed" should be less than their Cronbach's alphas. The figure in Table 1 designate all of the Cronbach's α s exceed the 0.7 value, ranging from 0.835 of Electronic word of mouth (MEW) to 0.853 of Destination image (DEI). Additionally, all of the highest Cronbach's α s "if item removed" are less than their own Cronbach's α s. Those findings determine the variables all meet satisfactory internal steadiness. Henceforward, they are all appropriate for subsequent analyses.

Table 1: Reliability analyses

Variables	Highest Cronbach's α s "if item removed"	Cronbach's α s	Number of items
Electronic word of mouth (MEW)	0.773	0.835	6
Destination image (DEI)	0.822	0.853	5
Intention to revisit (IRE).	0.813	0.846	3

Exploratory factor analyses

Exploratory factor analyses were undertaken to categorize the items to their own variables. The exploratory factor analyses were performed to explore variable validity. The conditions of the factor-loadings exceeding the 0.4 level were used to test convergent validity; whereas, the cross-loadings surpassing the 0.3 value were used to test discriminant validity (Murtagh, 1990). The figures in Table 2 only display the loadings larger than the 0.3 level. As shown in Table 2, the items are allocated to their own hypothetical specification of the variables. The loadings all exceed the 0.7 level. Therefore, the cross-loadings all surpass the 0.3 threshold, indicating the validity of discriminant as well as convergent. The communalities are all greater than the 0.5 value with the KMO of 0.862 smaller than the lowest satisfactory value at the statistical significance (P_{value} of 0.000) less than the 1% level, indicating that they should be retained for subsequent analyses (Murtagh, 1990).

Table 2: Exploratory factor analyses

Items	Loadings			Communalities
	1	2	3	
MEW	0.854			0.751
MEW	0.847			0.736
MEW	0.861			0.761
MEW	0.817			0.711
MEW	0.834			0.717
MEW	0.805			0.674
DEI		0.737		0.556
DEI		0.826		0.697
DEI		0.871		0.762
DEI		0.833		0.714
DEI		0.722		0.538
IRE			0.747	0.616
IRE			0.760	0.671
IRE			0.764	0.644
KMO/P _{value}	0.862/0.000			

Investigation of research hypotheses

From the aforementioned reliability and exploratory factor analyses, the findings guaranteed the internal reliability as well as the discriminant and convergent validity of the variables. Subsequently, the summed variables were calculated. To examine the anticipated hypotheses in the model, various regression analyses were undertaken. The empirical results are exhibited in Table 3. The empirical results demonstrate, research models of 1 & 2 obtain the goodness of fit at the significance value at the 1% level (the Fs of 38.568 & 48.526 with the P>|F|s of 0.000 & 0.000). In Model 1, the independent variable (Electronic word of mouth- MEW) explains 51.3% (R² of 0.513) of variance in the dependent variable (Destination image- DEI). In Model 2, the independent variable (Electronic word of mouth- MEW & Destination image- DEI) explains 62.7% (R² of 0.627) of variance in the dependent variable (Intention to revisit- IRE).

Table 2: Multiple regression analyses

Model	Independent variable	Dependent variable	B	S.E.	t	P> t	F	P> F	R ²
1	DEI	C	0.523	0.311	1.672	0.094	38.568	0.000	0.513
		MEW	2.881	0.284	10.108	0.000			
2	IRE	C	0.037	0.189	0.189	0.849	48.526	0.000	0.627
		MEW	4.502	0.861	5.219	0.000			
		DEI	0.775	0.354	2.193	0.028			

The findings also reveal, Electronic word of mouth- MEW positively influences Destination image- DEI at the 1% significance level with the estimate of 2.881 and positively affects Intention to revisit- IRE at the 1% significance level with the estimate of 4.502; whereas,

Destination image- DEI positively influences Intention to revisit- IRE at the 5% significance level with the estimate of 0.775. The findings are statistically significant in support for research hypotheses H1, H2 & H3, where Electronic word of mouth affects Intention to revisit and Destination image, which in turn influences also Intention to revisit.

CONCLUSION

The standard of life has been improved in the world. Therefore, an increasing number of people try to be going on holiday to various tourism attractions. The current research established the research model connected with the influences of electronic word of mouth on destination image and on intention to revisit as well as the effect of destination image on intention to revisit with using the case of visitors visiting the Tra Vinh city of Vietnam. The empirical results confirm the research hypotheses in which electronic word of mouth affects intention to revisit and destination image, that in turn influences intention to revisit.

The current research offers some important implications for marketers, administrators, and local government officials in the Tra Vinh city of Vietnam to improve electronic word of mouth and destination image. In addition, it also provides them a full understanding of the determining factors of visitors' intention to revisit the Tra Vinh city of Vietnam, which can help them to develop better policies to develop tourism in the Tra Vinh city of Vietnam.

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